

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

Grant Agreement No. 101036756

Deliverable 7.2

December 2023

Lab experiments on the fate of PM substances in lab-scale sludge treatment systems

Work Package 7 – Technical Solutions, Method
Development and Analysis

Deliverable Work Package Leader:
UNIVERSITY OF THE AEGEAN

Revision: 0
Dissemination level: **Public**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036756.

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The present document has not yet received final approval from the European Commission and may be subject to changes.

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Project information

Project period:
Duration (no. of months):
Web-site:
Project coordinator:

October 2021 to September 2026
60
www.zeropm.eu
Norwegian Geotechnical Institute, (NGI project no.: 20210423)

Project partners:

Summary

The European research project ZeroPM – “Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances” combines three interlinked strategies to tackle pollution with persistent and mobile substances: **Prevent**, **Prioritize** and **Remove**. Work Package 7 - “Technical Solutions, Method Development and Analysis” (WP7) is dedicated to the removal of these substances. Among other things, WP7 will develop innovative treatment methods such as a combination of advanced anaerobic digestion (AD) and hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) to remove persistent and mobile substances from sewage sludge. To achieve this, lab-scale experiments were conducted using sludge AD bioreactors, operated under mesophilic and thermophilic conditions. The possible effects of sludge pretreatment, application of direct voltage and addition of conductive materials in the bioreactor were evaluated by monitoring the system's performance and elimination of selected per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) and benzotriazoles (BTRs). In parallel, a high pressure/high temperature lab reactor was used to determine the removal of PFAS during hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) process. The role of temperature and pressure on the system's performance was evaluated. The concentrations of target PFAS was monitored in the solid, liquid and gaseous phase and mass balances were determined.

The present deliverable 7.2 describes the experimental conditions applied for the AD and HTC experiments (Section 2: Experimental). Results related to the role of different parameters on the performance of the tested processes and on the removal of target substances are provided in Section 3 (Results and Discussion). The annex of this report contains information on the analytical methods used for the measurement of different parameters and persistent and mobile substances.

Batch and continuous AD experiments using sewage sludge spiked with selected BTRs and PFAS were carried out in the presence of different conductive materials (graphite, granular activated carbon, magnetite, hydrochar), different voltage (0.8 V, 2 V), after thermal (80 °C, 105 °C) and ultrasound (200 Watt, 280 Watt, 360 Watt) sludge pretreatment and applying mesophilic (35 °C) and thermophilic (55 °C) conditions in the bioreactors. All BTRs were partially removed during AD while their removal efficiency was enhanced when granular activated carbon (GAC) was added to the bioreactors. No removal of target PFAS was recorded when conventional AD was applied. However, partial removal of certain PFAS was observed in the presence of GAC. Determination of the volume and the methane content of the produced biogas in AD batch experiments showed that the addition of graphite powder had no significant effect on methane productivity. However, the application of external voltage increased the maximum methane potential. Additionally, the presence of GAC had a positive effect on methane productivity while the application of ultrasound pretreatment increased both maximum biogas production rate and maximum biogas potential.

In HTC experiments, sewage sludge samples spiked with selected PFAS were treated at different temperatures (200°C, 250°C, and 300°C) with a 2-hour residence time, while for anaerobically digested sludge, experiments were conducted at 250°C under various pressures. The results showed that target PFAS can be removed during HTC of sewage

sludge and that the percentage removal is affected by the target compound and the applied experimental conditions. Increasing temperature enhanced PFAS removal. Analysis of target PFAS in the different phases of HTC indicated the detection of trace amounts of most of them in the gas phase. Additional analyses included assessments of chemical oxygen demand (COD), pH, ammonium nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$), and phytotoxicity testing of the produced hydrochars. Generally, COD and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ concentrations increased during HTC treatment, while pH values decreased. Phytotoxicity tests indicated a low germination index for the resulting hydrochars.

This deliverable is linked to the milestone MS13 (Construction of the pilot sludge treatment system) as results from lab work will be used to design the sewage sludge pilot scale system. Results will be used further as input data for task 2.5 within ZeroPM.

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Picture 2. Experimental set-up of CSTR experiments.

Appendix

- Determination of conventional pollutants and basic parameters
- Determination of BTRs
- Determination of PFAS
- High-throughput 16 S rRNA gene sequencing
- Phytotoxicity assessment

Table of Abbreviations

1H-BTR	1H-benzotriazole
5TTR	5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole
AD	Anaerobic digestion
BTRs	Benzotriazoles
CBTR	5-chlorobenzotriazole
CSTR	Continuous stirred-tank reactors
CM	Conductive material
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
FID	Flame ionization detector
GAC	Granular activated carbon
HHV	Higher heating value
HTC	Hydrothermal carbonization
PFAS	Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PFPeA	Perfluoropentanoic acid
PFHpA	Perfluoroheptanoic acid
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid
PFDA	Perfluoro-decanoic acid
PFUdA	Perfluoro-undecanoic acid
PFOS	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
PM	Persistent, mobile
SPE	Solid phase extraction
TCD	Thermal conductivity detector
TS	Total solids
US	Ultrasound treatment
VFAs	Volatile fatty acids
VS	Volatile solids
WP	Work package
XTR	Xylyltriazole

1. Introduction

ZeroPM, which stands for Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances, is a 5 year long European research project funded under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. ZeroPM will interlink and synergize three strategies to protect the environment and human health from persistent and mobile substances: **Prevent**, **Prioritize** and **Remove**. To do this, ZeroPM will develop an evidence-based multilevel framework. The framework will guide policy, technological and market incentives to minimize use, emissions and pollution of entire groups of persistent and mobile substances.

Work Package 7 – “Technical Solutions, Method Development and Analysis” (WP7) has the overall objective to demonstrate how and if legacy and prioritized persistent and mobile substance pollution can be remediated. WP7 investigates innovative treatment and monitoring methods for water and sludge to protect human health and the environment with a focus on persistent and mobile substances and media from three different test sites. To meet this goal, three test sites have been identified where various technical solutions will be developed and monitored. The test sites are in Germany (Rastatt and Upper Rhine – test sites 1 and 2 respectively) and Greece (Mytilene – test site 3).

The test site in Greece will be constructed in Lesbos Island (Mytilene, Greece) and will focus on the treatment of sewage sludge. In 2020 more than 8.9 million tonnes of sewage sludge were produced in the EU-27 countries (Statista, 2023). Within EU-27, according to the available Eurostat data (Eurostat, 2023), 35% of the produced sewage sludge was directly used in agriculture, 15% was composted, and 10% was landfilled. Sewage sludge is very often contaminated with persistent and mobile substances such as PFAS, benzotriazoles (BTRs) and other organic micropollutants (Wick et al., 2011; Arvaniti and Stasinakis, 2015; Kumar et al., 2022). Sludge treatment in the EU is typically carried out by applying mesophilic anaerobic digestion (AD) (Kelessidis and Stasinakis, 2012). However, this practice is characterised by a lack of integrated knowledge about the fate of diverse persistent and mobile substances (Winchell et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021). Additionally, modifications of the conventional AD system (via sludge pre-treatment, addition of voltage or conductive materials in the bioreactor) that improve performance and increase removal efficiency of conventional pollutants have not been tested for persistent and mobile substances. On the other hand, novel thermal processes such as hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) have begun attracting attention at lab and pilot scale during the last years for sludge and other biosolids treatment (Wang et al., 2019), for potential upscaling. This thermochemical process, that involves the conversion of organic materials into a carbon-rich solid product (hydrochar) under high-temperature and high-pressure conditions in the presence of water, offers specific advantages such as carbon sequestration, energy recovery, nutrient retention, reduction of pathogens and odours that are consistent with the aim of circular economy (Tasca et al., 2019). However, so far, no information is available for the fate of persistent and mobile substances during this process. This work addresses these gaps.

To select the appropriate conditions for the design and operation of the pilot-scale sewage sludge treatment plant that will combine improved AD and HTC processes, lab

experiments were conducted. The role of various parameters such as sludge pretreatment, application of direct voltage and addition of conductive materials were evaluated in mesophilic and thermophilic batch (biomethane potential) experiments as well as using continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTRs). A high pressure/high temperature lab reactor was also used and operated under different conditions to check the role of temperature, pressure, initial pH on persistent and mobile substances removal. The main objective of the hydrothermal experiments was to explore how the hydrothermal carbonization process impacts the degradation of PFAS in both sewage sludge and digested sludge, while also evaluating the potential of the resulting hydrochars for soil conditioning purposes.

The present report describes the experimental methodology that was applied and the main results that were obtained.

2. Task definition

As defined above, the pilot-scale system that will be constructed in Lesvos Island will combine advanced AD and HTC for the treatment of sewage sludge. As most of the persistent and mobile substances that are usually detected in sewage sludge are considered resistant to the conventional anaerobic biological treatment, the role of sludge pretreatment and the modification of conventional anaerobic digestion process using conductive materials or/and applying voltage in the bioreactor will be tested in order to achieve removal of target persistent and mobile substances. Additionally, the treatment of sewage sludge with HTC will be evaluated.

The experiments described in the current report aimed at (i) testing and comparing the addition of different conductive materials and the application of voltage during AD, the role of thermal and ultrasound sludge pretreatment as well as the role of mesophilic and thermophilic AD on the removal of selected BTRs and PFAS and (ii) studying the effect of HTC under different conditions on the removal of PFAS from sewage sludge. The results should enable a selection of operational conditions and processes that are more promising for the removal of persistent and mobile substances from sewage sludge. These conditions will then be applied at pilot-scale at the plant that will be constructed at Lesvos Island and become the follow up work to this deliverable.

3. Experimental

3.1 Advanced anaerobic digestion experiments

Two different types of anaerobic digestion lab experiments (batch and continuous) were conducted to examine the role of addition of conductive materials, application of voltage, sludge pretreatment and applied temperature in the bioreactors to the performance of AD process and removal of target persistent and mobile substances.

3.1.1 Batch experiments

Batch experiments were conducted in 120-mL glass serum bottles in order to determine the possible effect of the addition of conductive materials (CM) or/and the application of external voltage on persistent and mobile substances removal as well as biogas production (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic presentation of batch experiments testing the effect of external voltage application and/or conductive materials addition (graphite powder, granular activated carbon, magnetite, hydrochar) on persistent and mobile substances removal and biogas production.

In all experiments, serum bottles were sealed with butyl rubber stoppers and aluminium crimps, purged with nitrogen gas for approximately 1 minute to remove oxygen and were placed in a water bath at 37 °C for incubation (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Experimental set-up of batch experiments

Biogas produced was measured daily by the displacement of a piston of a gas-tight plastic syringe inserted into the bottles (Figure 2). Simultaneously, the methane content of the biogas was determined using a gas chromatography (6890N, Agilent) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID).

Figure 2. Schematic presentation of biogas measurement in serum bottles

The working volume of the batch reactors was 80 mL including 40 mL of sewage sludge and 40 mL of anaerobic inoculum. The inoculum originated from a pilot scale mesophilic anaerobic digester treating agro-industrial wastewater (University Campus, Lesvos Island). Different types of sewage sludge were tested including a) raw sewage sludge (mixture 30:70 of primary and secondary treated sludge), b) thermally pretreated sewage sludge and c) ultrasound pre-treated sewage sludge. In addition, four different conductive materials were tested including a) graphite powder, b) granular activated carbon (GAC), c) magnetite and d) hydrochar.

All experiments were conducted in duplicate, and there were also bottles that contained only inoculum without the addition of feedstock (blank). The reactors operated in fed-batch mode were done so by replacing approximately 40 mL of the mixed liquid in the digester with fresh sewage sludge at the end of each cycle. The duration of the cycle was determined based on the end of gas production, and the reactors were operated for a total of three batch cycles. In order to assess the efficiency of each reactor setup, the methane production over time was analysed by fitting it to the modified Gompertz equation in the following manner:

$$B(t) = B_o \exp \left\{ -\exp \left[\frac{R_m}{B_o} (\lambda - t)e + 1 \right] \right\}$$

where $B(t)$ is the cumulative methane production at time t (mL/gVS), B_o is the maximum methane potential (mL/gVS), R_m is the maximum methane production rate (mL/gVS/d), λ is the lag phase (d) and e is Euler's constant (2.718).

All the batch experiments included in this Deliverable are presented in Table 1. Information is provided for the experimental conditions used in each of them as well as about which persistent and mobile substances were added.

Table 1. List of batch experiments conducted during this reporting period.

Experiment	Experimental Conditions	Added persistent and mobile substances
	2 replicates per studied parameter, average duration of each experimental cycle: 2 months, inoculum: anaerobic sludge	Nominal concentrations of added substances: 100 µg/L
A	mesophilic conditions, application or not of voltage (0.8 V), addition or not of graphite powder (10 g/L), electrodes: stainless steel	BTRs: 1H-BTR, 5TTR, CBTR, XTR
B	mesophilic conditions, use or not of thermal pretreated sludge, in combination or not with GAC	BTRs: 1H-BTR, 5TTR, CBTR, XTR PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
C	BMP experiments with ultrasound pretreated sludge (20 KHz, 200 Watt, 280 Watt and 360 Watt for 15 min and 30 min) in combination or not with GAC	BTRs: 5TTR, CBTR, XTR PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
D	BMP experiments with different conductive materials (magnetite, hydrochar) and ultrasound pretreated or thermally pretreated sludge	PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS

3.1.2 Continuous experiments

Continuous experiments were conducted in 1-L modified glass flasks operated as anaerobic digesters under draw and fill mode in order to examine the long-term effect of external voltage application and/or GAC addition on persistent and mobile substances removal and biogas productivity (*Picture 2*). Reactor #1 was a typical AD reactor, in Reactor #2 an external voltage was applied, Reactor #3 contained GAC while in Reactor #4 GAC and voltage were applied. Two different voltages (0.8 V and 2.0 V) were tested. The electrodes in Reactors #2 and #4 were made of carbon cloth.

Picture 2. Experimental set-up of CSTR experiments.

The AD reactors operated at a HRT of 20 days under mesophilic (37 °C) or thermophilic (55 °C) conditions. The pH was monitored on a daily basis, while biogas volume and methane content were measured twice a week. Biogas was collected in 2-L plastic bags and then measured using a drum-type Gas meter (TG1, Ritter). Methane content was measured using a portable biogas analyzer (Biogas 5000, Geotech) Samples were taken twice a week from the influents and effluents for COD, TS, VS and VFAs and once a week for the target microcontaminants. Different types of sewage sludge were tested including a) raw sewage sludge (mixture 30:70 of primary and secondary treated sludge), b) thermally pretreated sewage sludge, and c) ultrasound pretreated sewage sludge.

All the continuous experiments that were conducted during this reporting period are presented in Table 2. Information is also provided for the experimental conditions used and the persistent and mobile substances added. For the evaluation of possible differences on the microbial profile of the sludge in different bioreactors, samples were taken at the end of the experiment conducted under thermophilic conditions (Experiment D) and high-throughput 16 S rRNA gene sequencing was applied.

Table 2. List of continuous experiments conducted during this reporting period

Experiment	Conditions tested	Experimental Conditions average duration of each experiment: 3 months, inoculum: anaerobic sludge	Added persistent and mobile substances nominal concentrations of added substances: 100 µg/L
A	Role of GAC and voltage application (0.8 V)	4 reactors in parallel: Typical AD, AD + GAC, AD + voltage, AD + GAC + voltage Mesophilic conditions (37 °C)	BTRs: 1H-BTR, 5TTR, CBTR, XTR
B	Role of GAC and increased voltage application (2 V)	4 reactors in parallel: Typical AD, AD + GAC, AD + voltage, AD + GAC + voltage Mesophilic conditions (37 °C)	BTRs: 1H-BTR, 5TTR, CBTR, XTR PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
C	Role of GAC/voltage (2V) AND use of thermally pretreated sewage sludge (80 °C, 1 h)	4 reactors in parallel: Typical AD, AD + GAC, AD + voltage, AD + GAC + voltage Mesophilic conditions (37 °C)	BTRs: 1H-BTR, 5TTR, CBTR, XTR PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
D	Role of GAC/voltage (0.8V)	4 reactors in parallel: Typical AD, AD + GAC, AD + voltage, AD + GAC + voltage Thermophilic conditions (55 °C)	BTRs: 1H-BTR, 5TTR, CBTR, XTR PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
E	Role of GAC/voltage (2V) AND use of ultrasound pretreated sewage sludge (320 Watt, 15 min)	4 reactors in parallel: Typical AD, AD + GAC, AD + voltage, AD + GAC + voltage Mesophilic conditions (37 °C)	BTRs: 1H-BTR, 5TTR, CBTR, XTR PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS

3.2 Hydrothermal carbonization experiments

Secondary sewage sludge sourced from the Mytilene wastewater treatment plant on Lesvos Island and anaerobically digested sludge from an upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactor in Antissa village (Lesvos Island) were sampled for the experimental procedures in this study. After collection, both sludges were separated from the supernatant water and were stored for the subsequent experiments. Following

this separation, the sewage sludge exhibited a total solids (TS) content of 1.3% (12.3 g/L), while the anaerobically digested sludge contained 7% TS (61.2 g/L).

A total of two sets of nine experiments were carried out utilising a 1 L capacity Parr 4577A hydrothermal reactor. In the initial series, the first three experiments served as Blank-Control tests, employing sewage sludge as the raw material. These experiments were conducted under varying temperature-pressure conditions, with a pH of 7 and a residence time of 2 hours. The three subsequent experiments followed the same conditions as the Blank-Control experiments but included the introduction of selected PFAS. The final three experiments emulated the conditions of the previous set, with the exception of the pH, which was adjusted to 9 using NaOH. In all cases the role of elevated pressure on the characteristics of the products was examined. Details of the experiments are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) experiments conducted during this reporting period.

Experiment	Studied Parameters duration 2 h, addition of persistent and mobile substances at 100 µg/L	Added persistent and mobile substances
A	Role of temperature : 200, 250 °C, 300 °C	PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
B	Role of pH : 7, 9 (using NaOH)	PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
C	Role of P : 40, 65 bars (at 250 °C)	PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
D	Role of NaOH	PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
E	Comparison with different sludges	PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS
F	Application of a mass balances (mass yield of hydrochar)	PFAS: PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS

Mass balances are essential tools which allow the conservation of mass within a system to be accounted for. These balances involve the meticulous tracking of mass inputs, outputs, and accumulations to gain a comprehensive understanding of how materials move and transform within a given process or system. By applying the principles of mass conservation, mass balances enable the quantification of material flows, the identification of potential losses or inefficiencies, and the optimization of processes to minimise waste and resource consumption. Mass balances provide valuable insights into the management and sustainability of processes, helping to ensure that resources are utilised efficiently, and waste generation is minimised.

As shown in Table 3, mass balance experiments were conducted during Experiment F. In total, 8 different samples were included for the flows as shown in Figure 3. With respect to the inflows, the sludges used were separated into liquid and suspended solid samples. The products of HTC were distributed among all the phases and the gaseous part was separated further downstream from the contained tar compounds before the final measurements. Using this framework allowed the totality of inflows and outflows of the HTC process to be measured and accounted for.

Figure 3. Representation of the sampling points during HTC of sludge used to determine mass balances (Experiment F).

After HTC experiments, the collected samples were analyzed for target PFAS according to the methods described in the Appendix. Additionally, a range of other parameters were measured to characterise the resulting products. These included COD analysis for the liquid products, ammonium nitrogen and pH measurements for the liquid output, and a phytotoxicity assessment to determine the suitability of the produced hydrochars for use as soil conditioners. Figure 4 provides an overview of the methods of analysis that were utilised in this study.

Figure 4. The total series of analytical methods that were implemented in HTC experiments.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Advanced anaerobic digestion experiments

4.1.1 Batch experiments

4.1.1.1 Experiment A (Application of external voltage and graphite powder)

Figure 5 illustrates the specific methane production during the four different experimental setups. Results showed that the addition of graphite powder had no important effect on methane productivity. However, the application of external voltage increased the maximum methane potential.

Figure 5. Cumulative methane production during the batch cycle and modified Gompertz model fit using experimental data. **AD**: typical anaerobic digestion; **AD-G**: anaerobic digestion with the addition of graphite powder; **AD-V**: anaerobic digestion with the application of external voltage (0.8 V); **AD-GV**: anaerobic digestion with the addition of graphite powder and the application of external voltage (0.8 V)

The values for the maximum methane potential and the maximum methane production rate, estimated by fitting raw data with Gompertz equation, are presented in Table 4. The application of the external voltage increased the maximum methane potential by 14% compared to typical anaerobic digestion (from 355.5 mL/gVS to 405.8 mL/gVS)

Table 4. The estimated values of a) maximum methane potential (B_0), b) maximum methane production rate (R_m) and c) lag phase (λ), according to the modified Gompertz equation.

Parameter	AD	AD-V	AD-G	AD-GV
B_0	355.5 ± 9.0	405.8 ± 12.3	359.3 ± 10.3	374.5 ± 10.6
R_m	40.7 ± 2.6	40.7 ± 1.4	39.6 ± 2.8	39.4 ± 1.3
λ	0.2 ± 0.3	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.3	0.0 ± 0.0
R^2	0.991	0.986	0.987	0.986

Different removal of target BTRs was observed during the AD experiments as shown in Figure 6. BTR and XTR were removed by more than 70% and 90%, respectively, 5TTR was removed by 27 to 37%, while CBTR was not removed. Biotransformation is expected to be the main mechanism responsible for BTRs removal, the role of sorption was of minor importance. The ability of anaerobic sludge to biodegrade target BTRs did not appear to be affected by the application of voltage or/and the addition of graphite.

Figure 6. Removal of target BTRs during AD batch experiment A. BTR: benzotriazole; 5TTR: 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole; CBTR: chlorobenzotriazole; XTR: xlyltriazole

Table 5. The estimated values of a) maximum methane potential (B_0), b) maximum methane production rate (R_m) and c) lag phase (λ), according to the modified Gompertz equation.

Parameter	Untreated	80 °C-1h	80 °C-3h	105 °C-1h	105 °C-3h
B_0	321 ± 6	308 ± 6	631 ± 33	300 ± 7	659 ± 39
R_m	22.5 ± 1.1	21.1 ± 1.1	11.8 ± 0.3	12.9 ± 0.9	9.7 ± 0.2
λ	<0.1	<0.1	6.0 ± 0.6	0.7 ± 0.8	7.5 ± 0.5
R^2	0.95	0.94	0.99	0.97	0.99

Parameter	untreated + GAC	80 °C-1h + GAC	80 °C-3h + GAC	105 °C-1h + GAC	105 °C-3h + GAC
B_0	432 ± 6	440 ± 10	385 ± 6	415 ± 7	438 ± 3
R_m	24.0 ± 0.9	17.9 ± 0.7	18.0 ± 0.5	16.5 ± 0.4	18.8 ± 0.2
λ	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
R^2	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.99

Analysis of BTRs in the different flasks used during Experiment B showed that they can be biodegraded by strictly anaerobic bacteria (Figure 8). The removal of target substances was increased when GAC was added. Concerning the role of thermal pretreatment, its effect on BTRs removal was not clear. For specific compounds and conditions, an enhancement of their removal was noticed. For instance, the application of 80 °C or 105 °C for a period of 1 hour enhanced the removal of CBTR while the thermal pretreatment at 80 °C for 3 hours improved the removal of 5-TTR.

Figure 8. Removal of BTRs in different experimental conditions tested during AD batch experiment B. **BTR:** benzotriazole; **5TTR:** 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole; **CBTR:** chlorobenzotriazole; **XTR:** xylylriazole

Removal of all studied PFAS was observed in the flasks containing GAC. The highest removal was 68% for PFPeA (AD-GAC), 81% for PFOA (AD-GAC, 80 °C, 1 h), 82% for PFNA (AD-GAC, 80 °C, 1 h), 80% for total PFOS (AD-GAC, 80 °C, 1 h), 77% for PFDA (AD-GAC), and 72% for PFUdA (AD-GAC) (Figure 9). In the experimental flasks containing no GAC, the removal was much lower, not exceeding 39% for PFUdA. Regarding the role of thermal pre-treatment, a slight increase of PFAS removal was observed when thermal pretreatment of sewage sludge was applied at 80 °C/3h.

Figure 9. Removal of PFAS in different experimental conditions tested during AD batch experiment B. **PFPeA:** perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFOA:** perfluorooctanoic acid; **PFNA:** perfluorononanoic acid; **PFOS:** perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; **PFDA:** perfluorodecanoic acid; **PFUdA:** perfluoro-undecanoic acid

4.1.1.3 Experiment C (Addition of GAC and use of ultrasound pretreated sludge)

Figure 10 illustrates the specific biogas production during the first batch cycle for the different experimental setups. Results showed that the addition of GAC increased methane productivity. In addition, the application of ultrasound pretreatment increased both maximum biogas production rate and maximum biogas potential.

Figure 10. Cumulative biogas production during the first batch cycle and modified Gompertz model fit using experimental data. **Control:** typical anaerobic digestion with untreated sludge; Experimental setups for anaerobic digestion with pretreated sludge, where the pret are represented by “XXX_YY(_GAC)” where XXX is the Wattage (W), YY the duration (minutes) and GAC indicates if GAC was added, e.g. **200-15:** anaerobic digestion with ultrasound pretreated sludge using 200W for 15 min.

The values for the maximum biogas potential and the maximum biogas production rate, estimated by fitting raw data with Gompertz equation for the second cycle, are presented in Table 6. The lag phase values in the ultrasound treated sludge using 360 W were found to be slightly higher, suggesting that the microbial biomass was inhibited.

Table 6. The estimated values of a) maximum methane potential (B_0), b) maximum methane production rate (R_m) and c) lag phase (λ), according to the modified Gompertz equation.

Parameter	B_0	R_m	λ	R^2
control	361 ± 9	36.2 ± 1.2	<0.1	0.98
200-15	413 ± 7	43.0 ± 1.1	<0.1	0.99
200-15-GAC	413 ± 8	44.2 ± 1.3	<0.1	0.99
200-30	386 ± 7	42.7 ± 1.1	<0.1	0.99
200-30-GAC	370 ± 6	44.5 ± 1.4	<0.1	0.99
280-15	362 ± 7	46.6 ± 1.6	<0.1	0.99
280-15-GAC	369 ± 7	46.8 ± 1.6	<0.1	0.98
280-30	396 ± 8	37.8 ± 1.3	<0.1	0.99
280-30-GAC	398 ± 6	41.8 ± 1.8	0.2 ± 0.2	0.99
360-15	384 ± 5	39.7 ± 1.6	0.4 ± 0.2	0.99
360-15-GAC	411 ± 4	51.5 ± 1.6	0.6 ± 0.1	0.99
360-30	404 ± 5	42.9 ± 1.5	0.4 ± 0.2	0.99
360-30-GAC	387 ± 5	47.2 ± 1.8	0.5 ± 0.2	0.99

As regards the removal of BTRs, no significant removal (<25%) was noticed in the experiments that conducted in the absence of GAC. On the other hand, the addition of GAC resulted to full removal of 5TTR in all experimental flasks, CBTR was removed at percentages that ranged between 29 and 96% while XTR at percentages between 27 and 100% (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Removal of BTRs in different experimental conditions tested during AD batch experiment D. **BTR:** benzotriazole; **5TTR:** 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole; **CBTR:** chlorobenzotriazole; **XTR:** xylytriazole

Determination of the total mass of target PFAS in samples collected at the start and end of the experiments showed that all PFAS were partially removed in the experimental flasks containing GAC (Figure 12). The removal efficiency ranged up to 50% for PFPeA (280 Watt, 15 min), 75% for PFHpA (280 Watt, 15 min), 75% for PFOA (200 Watt, 15 min), 61% for PFNA (200 Watt, 15 min), 70% for PFDA (280 Watt, 30 min), 38% for PFUdA (280 Watt, 30 min), 43% for linear PFOS (280 Watt, 30 min), and 51% for branched PFOS (200 Watt, 15 min). On the other hand, in the experimental flasks where no GAC had been added, there was no significant removal of target PFAS (<25%).

Figure 12. Removal of PFAS in different experimental conditions tested during AD batch experiment D. **PFPeA:** perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFHpA:** Perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFOA:** perfluorooctanoic acid; **PFNA:** perfluorononanoic acid; **L-PFOS:** linear perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; **Br-PFOS:** branched perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; **PFDA:** perfluorodecanoic acid; **PFUdA:** perfluoro-undecanoic acid

4.1.1.4 Experiment D (Application of different conductive materials and ultrasound pretreated or thermally pretreated sludge)

Figure 13 illustrates the cumulative methane production during the batch cycle for the various experimental setups. The results showed that thermally pretreated sludge had a positive effect on methane productivity. Furthermore, the addition of hydrochar or magnetite to thermally pretreated sludge increased both the maximum biogas production rate and the maximum biogas potential. By contrast, the addition of hydrochar to untreated or ultrasound-treated sludge had a potentially toxic effect on the process.

Figure 13. Cumulative methane production during the batch cycle and modified Gompertz model fit using experimental data. **Control:** typical anaerobic digestion with untreated sludge; **Control+ substances:** typical anaerobic digestion with untreated sludge spiked with PFAs and benzotriazoles; **Hydrochar:** anaerobic digestion with untreated sludge with the addition of Hydrochar (20 g/L); **Magnetite:** anaerobic digestion with untreated sludge with the addition of Magnetite (10 g/L); **US:** anaerobic digestion with ultrasound pretreated sludge; **US-Hydrochar:** anaerobic digestion with ultrasound pretreated sludge with the addition of Hydrochar (20 g/L); **US-Magnetite:** anaerobic digestion with ultrasound pretreated sludge with the addition of Magnetite (10 g/L); **Thermal:** anaerobic digestion with thermally pretreated sludge; **Thermal-Hydrochar:** anaerobic digestion with thermally pretreated sludge with the addition of Hydrochar (20 g/L); **Thermal-Magnetite:** anaerobic digestion with thermally pretreated sludge with the addition of Magnetite (10 g/L)

The values for the maximum biogas potential and the maximum biogas production rate, estimated by fitting raw data with Gompertz equation for the second cycle, are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. The estimated values of a) maximum methane potential (B_0), b) maximum methane production rate (R_m) and c) lag phase (λ), according to the modified Gompertz equation.

Parameter	B_0	R_m	λ	R^2
Control	617 ± 10	30.2 ± 0.9	2.5 ± 0.2	0.99
Control+ substances	666 ± 11	30.0 ± 0.8	1.7 ± 0.2	0.99
Hydrochar	415 ± 9	19.8 ± 0.8	0.3 ± 0.4	0.99
Magnetite	624 ± 11	29.0 ± 0.8	1.7 ± 0.3	0.99
US	706 ± 7	48.2 ± 1.3	4.0 ± 0.2	0.99
US-Hydrochar	437 ± 4	32.6 ± 0.9	3.1 ± 0.2	0.99
US-Magnetite	605 ± 5	39.6 ± 0.9	2.7 ± 0.2	0.99
Thermal	760 ± 9	56.5 ± 2.1	4.4 ± 0.2	0.99
Thermal- Hydrochar	1125 ± 23	49.4 ± 1.4	2.7 ± 0.2	0.99
Thermal- Magnetite	1030 ± 14	54.7 ± 1.5	2.6 ± 0.2	0.99

Determination of the total mass of target PFAS in samples collected at the start and end of the experiments showed that PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA and PFOS were not removed in any of the experimental flasks. On the other hand, significant removal (≥ 25) of PFDA and PFUdA was observed under specific experimental conditions (Table 8).

Table 8. Removal of PFDA and PFUdA in BMP experiments with different conductive materials (hydrochar, magnetite) and ultrasound of thermal pretreatment of sludge.

Removal (%)	PFDA	PFUdA
AD	No removal	No removal
AD-Hydrochar	46	No removal
AD-Magnetite	No removal	25
AD-US	26	No removal
AD-US-Hydrochar	No removal	No removal
AD-US-Magnetite	59	100
AD-Thermal	100	100
AD-Thermal-Hydrochar	100	100
AD-Thermal-Magnetite	No removal	No removal

4.1.2 Continuous experiments

4.1.2.1 Experiment A (Application of 0.8V external voltage and GAC, mesophilic)

Figure 14 illustrates the variation of pH during the experiments. pH values in all reactors were around 7.2 at steady state.

Figure 14. Variation of pH during the continuous AD experiment A. *AD*: typical anaerobic digestion; *AD-GAC*: anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC; *AD-V*: anaerobic digestion with the application of external voltage (0.8 V); *AD-GAC-V*: anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC and the application of external voltage (0.8 V)

The dissolved COD variation during the experiments is presented in Figure 15. An increase in COD was recorded at the final stage of the experiment. In addition, dissolved COD increased in the influents at this time.

Figure 15. Variation of d-COD during the continuous AD experiment A.

Figure 16 illustrates the variation of volatile solids (VS) during the experiments. The average VS concentration at steady state was found to be 18.5 ± 1.5 g/L, 24.5 ± 2.7 g/L, 24.6 ± 3.6 g/L and 19.8 ± 3.9 g/L in the reactor #1 (AD-V), #2 (AD-GAC-V), #3 (AD-GAC) and #4 (AD-V), respectively. The average VS removal at steady state was found to be 24%, 21%, 21% and 19%, in reactor 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Figure 16. Variation of VS during the continuous AD experiment A.

Figure 17 illustrates the average daily biogas production during the steady state of the experiment. Here methane content was around 62-64% in all reactors (Figure 18).

Figure 17. Average biogas production during steady state of the continuous AD experiment A.

Figure 18. Methane content in reactors during steady state during the continuous AD experiment A.

Analysis of target BTRs during the experiments showed that the removal of all BTRs was quite low (<45%) in the conventional AD reactor as well as in the reactor where 0.8 V voltage was applied (AD-V) (Figure 19). However, their removal significantly increased and exceeded 97% in the reactors containing GAC. There was no PFAS removal in any of the AD reactors used.

Figure 19. Removal of target BTRs in continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment A). BTR: benzotriazole; 5TTR: 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole; CBTR: chlorobenzotriazole; XTR: xylotriazole

4.1.2.2 Experiment B (Application of 2.0 V external voltage and GAC, mesophilic)

Figure 20 illustrates the variation of pH during the experiments. The average pH in all reactors were slightly higher (7.0-7.1) compared to the feed (6.8).

Figure 20. Variation of pH during the continuous AD experiment B. **AD:** typical anaerobic digestion; **AD-GAC:** anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC; **AD-V:** anaerobic digestion with the application of external voltage (2V); **AD-GAC-V:** anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC and the application of external voltage (2V)

The dissolved COD variation during the experiments is presented in Figure 21. The d-COD ranged from 500-1500 mg/L in all reactors.

Figure 21. Variation of d-COD during the continuous AD experiment B.

Figure 22 illustrates the variation of VS during the experiments. The average VS concentration in the reactors was found to be 16.1 ± 1.3 g/L, 21.4 ± 4.2 g/L, 18.5 ± 3.5 g/L and 17.3 ± 5.3 g/L in the reactor #1 (AD-V), #2 (AD-GAC-V), #3 (AD-GAC) and #4 (AD-V), respectively. The average VS removal was found to be 13%, 14%, 25% and 6%, in reactor 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Figure 22. Variation of VS during the continuous AD experiment B.

Figure 23 illustrates the average methane production during the steady state of the experiment. The methane content was around 62-64% in all reactors.

Figure 23. Average methane production during steady state of the continuous AD experiment B.

Analysis of target BTRs during the experiments showed that the removal of all BTRs increased compared to the previous experiment (Experiment A) in the conventional AD reactor as well as in the reactor where 2 V voltage was applied (AD-V). The addition of GAC enhanced the removal of most substances (Figure 24). There was no removal of PFAS in the conventional AD reactor and in the AD reactor where voltage was applied. On the other hand, selected PFAS (e.g. PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA) were removed at more than 45% in the AD reactors containing GAC (Figure 25).

Figure 24. Removal of target BTRs in continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment B). **BTR:** benzotriazole; **5TTR:** 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole; **CBTR:** chlorobenzotriazole; **XTR:** xylyltriazole

Figure 25. Removal (or formation) of target PFAS in continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment B). **PFPeA:** perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFHpA:** Perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFOA:** perfluorooctanoic acid; **PFNA:** perfluorononanoic acid; **PFOS:** Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; **PFDA:** perfluorodecanoic acid; **PFUdA:** perfluoro-undecanoic acid

4.1.2.3 Experiment C (Application of 2.0 V external voltage and GAC using thermally pretreated sludge, mesophilic)

Figure 26 illustrates the variation of pH during the experiments. The average pH in all reactors ranged from 6.8 to 7.0.

Figure 26. Variation of pH during the experiments with thermally pretreated sludge. **AD**: typical anaerobic digestion; **AD-GAC**: anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC; **AD-V**: anaerobic digestion with the application of external voltage (2V); **AD-GAC-V**: anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC and the application of external voltage (2V)

The dissolved COD variation during the experiments is presented in Figure 27. Due to thermal pretreatment the d-COD in the influent was quite high (4220 ± 1165 mg/L). However, the d-COD in reactors where voltage was applied or where GAC was added remained low (<1000 mg/L).

Figure 27. Variation of d-COD during the experiments with thermally pretreated sludge.

Figure 28 illustrates the variation of VS during the experiments. The average VS concentration in the reactors was found to be 13.4 ± 2.8 g/L, 14.5 ± 3.2 g/L, 12.3 ± 2.7 g/L and 11.4 ± 2.3 g/L in the reactor #1 (AD-V), #2 (AD-GAC-V), #3 (AD-GAC) and #4 (AD-V), respectively. The average VS removal was found to be 22%, 43%, 52% and 34%, in reactor 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Figure 28. Variation of VS during the experiments with thermally pretreated sludge.

Figure 29 illustrates the average daily methane production during the steady state of the experiment. No significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed. Methane content was around 62-64% in all reactors.

Figure 29. Average methane production during steady state of the experiment with thermally pretreated sludge.

Analysis of BTRs in different reactors showed that the thermal pretreatment of sludge did not enhance the removal of target compounds in the conventional AD reactor and in the reactor where voltage was applied. In accordance to the previous experiments, high removal of BTRs was observed in the reactors containing GAC (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Removal of target BTRs in continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment C) **BTR**: benzotriazole; **5TTR**: 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole; **CBTR**: chlorobenzotriazole; **XTR**: xylylriazole

The addition of GAC to the bioreactor enhanced also the removal of PFAS during AD. As a result, removal efficiencies ranging between 50 and 60% were observed in the reactor AD-AC for most target compounds (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Removal of target PFAS in continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment C). **PFPeA:** perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFHpA:** Perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFOA:** perfluorooctanoic acid; **PFNA:** perfluorononanoic acid; **PFOS:** Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; **PFDA:** perfluorodecanoic acid; **PFUdA:** perfluoro-undecanoic acid

4.1.2.4 Experiment D (Application of 0.8 V external voltage and GAC, thermophilic)

Figure 32 illustrates the variation of pH during the experiments under thermophilic conditions (55 °C). The average pH in all reactors was slightly higher compared to mesophilic experiments and ranged from 7.2 to 7.4.

Figure 32. Variation of pH during the experiments under thermophilic conditions. **AD:** typical anaerobic digestion; **AD-GAC:** anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC; **AD-V:** anaerobic digestion with the application of external voltage (0.8 V); **AD-GAC-V:** anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC and the application of external voltage (0.8 V)

The dissolved COD variation during the experiments is presented in Figure 33. The d-COD in the effluent of all reactors were higher compared to the influent. Thermophilic conditions seem to enhance the hydrolysis step.

Figure 33. Variation of d-COD during the experiments under thermophilic conditions.

Figure 34 illustrates the variation of VS during the experiments. The average VS concentration in the reactors at steady state was found to be 14.5 ± 4.2 g/L, 12.8 ± 2.6 g/L, 15.7 ± 6.1 g/L and 13.7 ± 4.5 g/L in the reactor #1 (AD-V), #2 (AD-GAC-V), #3 (AD-GAC) and #4 (AD-V), respectively. The average VS removal at steady state was found to be 30%, 50%, 36% and 37%, in reactor 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Figure 34. Variation of VS during the experiments under thermophilic conditions.

Figure 35 illustrates the average daily methane production during the steady state of the experiment. The steady state is assumed to be reached after 57 days of reactors operation. A higher average methane daily production (177 ± 71 mL/d) was observed in the reactor containing GAC. However, statistical analysis showed that this difference was not significant ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 35. Average methane production during steady state of the experiment under thermophilic conditions.

Upon comparing the relative abundance at the phylum level at the end of this experiment, *Coprothermobacterota* emerged as the most dominant phylum in the AD, AD+GAC, and AD+voltage bioreactors, and was the second most abundant in the AD+GAC+voltage system (Figure 36). At the genus level, *Coprothermobacter* was the most dominant across all systems. *Coprothermobacter* are strictly anaerobic, thermophilic, proteolytic, and hydrogen-producing organisms known for their capability to generate hydrogen through acetate oxidation and for forming growth-promoting syntrophic interactions with methanogens in anaerobic digesters (Dessi et al., 2019).

Figure 36. Relative abundance at the phylum level in the four anaerobic bioreactors.

BTRs were removed significantly in all bioreactors. In accordance with previous experiments, the addition of GAC enhanced the removal of most target substances (Figure 37). Specifically for BTR and XTR, the average removal exceeded 99.5% in the presence of GAC.

Figure 37. Removal of target BTRs in thermophilic continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment D). **BTR:** benzotriazole; **5TTR:** 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole; **CBTR:** chlorobenzotriazole; **XTR:** xylytriazole

Concerning PFAS, PFDA and PFUdA were not removed in none of the studied bioreactors. On the other hand, removal was observed for PFPeA that reached 80% in 3 out of 4 bioreactors. For the other target PFAS, removal rates equal to or above 40% were observed in the reactors containing GAC (Figure 38).

Figure 38. Removal (and formation) of target PFAS in thermophilic continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment D). **PFPeA:** perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFHpA:** Perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFOA:** perfluorooctanoic acid; **PFNA:** perfluorononanoic acid; **PFOS:** Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; **PFDA:** perfluorodecanoic acid; **PFUdA:** perfluoro-undecanoic acid

4.1.2.5 Experiment E (Application of 2.0 V external voltage and GAC using ultrasound pretreated sludge, mesophilic)

Figure 39 illustrates the variation of pH during the experiments with ultrasound pretreated sludge. The average pH in all reactors ranged from 6.9 to 7.2. The average pH in the feed was slightly higher (7.3).

Figure 39. Variation of pH during the experiments with ultrasound pretreated sludge. **AD**: typical anaerobic digestion; **AD-GAC**: anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC; **AD-V**: anaerobic digestion with the application of external voltage (2V); **AD-GAC-V**: anaerobic digestion with the addition of GAC and the application of external voltage (2V)

The dissolved COD variation during the experiments is presented in Figure 40. Due to ultrasound pretreatment the d-COD in the influent was slightly higher (1700 ± 818 mg/L). However, the d-COD in all reactors remained low (<900 mg/L).

Figure 40. Variation of d-COD during the experiments with ultrasound pretreated sludge.

Figure 41 illustrates the variation of VS during the experiment. The average VS concentration in the reactors was found to be 16.0 ± 2.5 g/L, 20.7 ± 7.8 g/L, 18.2 ± 5.0 g/L and 15.4 ± 2.2 g/L in the reactor #1 (AD-V), #2 (AD-GAC-V), #3 (AD-GAC) and #4 (AD-V), respectively. The average VS removal was found to be 15%, 15%, 25% and 18%, in reactor 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Figure 40. Variation of VS during the experiments with ultrasound pretreated sludge.

Figure 42 illustrates the average daily methane production during the steady state of the experiment. It is notable that the methane production in all reactors was lower than previous experiments which may be related to the characteristics of the sewage sludge used during the experiments.

Figure 41. Average methane production during the experiments with ultrasound pretreated sludge.

All target BTRs were partially removed using conventional AD. Their removal ranged between 55 and 80%. The addition of GAC in the bioreactors enhanced removal. As a result, BTR and 5-TTR were removed at greater than 99% (Figure 43).

Figure 42. Removal of target BTRs in continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment E). **BTR**: benzotriazole; **5TTR**: 5-methyl-1H-benzotriazole; **CBTR**: chlorobenzotriazole; **XTR**: xylotriazole

The use of conventional AD and the application of voltage in conventional bioreactors (AD and AD-V) did not result to PFAS removal. However, removal of most PFAS occurred in the bioreactors containing GAC (Figure 44).

Figure 43. Removal (and formation) of target PFAS in continuous-flow AD reactors (Experiment E). **PFPeA:** perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFHpA:** Perfluoropentanoic acid; **PFOA:** perfluorooctanoic acid; **PFNA:** perfluorononanoic acid; **PFOS:** Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; **PFDA:** perfluorodecanoic acid; **PFUnDA:** perfluoro-undecanoic acid

4.2. Hydrothermal carbonization experiments

Previous studies have shown mass yields of hydrochar produced through hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) vary widely depending on the feedstock and process conditions (Zhi et al. 2024). Mixing low-grade coal with municipal solids in combined HTC processes can improve both the yield and quality of hydrochar. This improvement is a result of chemical processes such as aromatization and dehydration, which are further influenced by the addition of substances like food waste and residues from cow dung biogas. On the other hand, treating standard lignocellulosic biomass with HTC at higher thermal levels usually results in a reduced yield of hydrochar. This reduction is primarily due to the breakdown and hydrolysis of components like cellulose and hemicellulose in the biomass (Zhi et al. 2024). Additionally, elevating the temperature of the reaction markedly lowers the hydrochar yield. A clear example of this is seen in lignocellulose, where the yield drops from 69.1% to 50.1% as the temperature increases from 215°C to 255°C. This decline is largely attributed to the conversion of condensable elements into gases that do not condense and the creation of total organic carbon in the resultant liquid products. A similar pattern of reduced hydrochar yield with increased HTC temperatures is noted across various types of feedstocks (Zhi et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2018). Generally, mass yield during HTC typically ranges from 10% to 50% on a dry weight basis. Factors influencing mass yields include the composition of the starting material, the severity of the hydrothermal treatment (e.g., temperature, residence time, pressure), and the presence of additives or catalysts. Materials rich in organic carbon, such as sewage sludge or lignocellulosic biomass, tend to yield higher amounts of hydrochar. Achieving a balance between maximizing the production of hydrochar and minimizing process by-products is a critical consideration for optimizing HTC processes. Understanding these mass yield variations is essential for both the efficient utilization of feedstocks and the sustainable production of hydrochar, which has applications in areas ranging from bioenergy production to soil conditioning and environmental remediation. Hydrochar exhibits heating values that typically fall within the range of 15 to 30 megajoules per kilogram (MJ/kg). However, these values can vary significantly depending on several factors, including the feedstock composition, process conditions (temperature, residence time, pressure), and post-treatment procedures. Hydrochar's relatively high heating values make it a promising bioenergy resource with potential applications in various thermal processes, such as combustion, gasification, or co-firing with other fuels.

Figure 45 presents the produced hydrochar yields from HTC of sludge from our analysis, along with their heating values that were found to be at the upper ranges of mass yield and heating value.

Figure 44. Hydrochar HHV and mass yield for different HTC experiments.

Figure 46 illustrates the percentage (%) of total PFAS removal for each experiment carried out at varying temperature levels during the HTC process of secondary sewage sludge. The results generally indicate high removal of PFAS under these treatment conditions, with the highest removal rates observed in experiments conducted at elevated temperatures.

Figure 45. PFAS removal (%) in HTC experiments of secondary sewage sludge under three different temperature values (200°C, 250°C, 300°C)

Zhang et al. (2020) suggested that carboxylate intermediates with shorter chains, like PFPeA, exhibited lower stability when exposed to high-temperature compressed water compared to their non-fluorinated alkylcarboxylic acid counterparts. Regarding the fate of PFOA, Yu et al., (2020) demonstrated that at 300 °C, a defluorination rate of approximately $30 \pm 6\%$ was achieved for PFOA. In contrast, PFOS remained largely unaffected under these conditions, with no fluoride detected in the water phase even at 350 °C. Furthermore, a study on sewage sludge treatment at 260 °C indicated a 35% reduction in PFOS, but the reduction rate remained consistent despite increasing the temperature to 350 °C or prolonging the treatment duration from 30 to 90 minutes. This varying resistance to degradation between PFOA and PFOS suggests that the initial degradation reactions in HT conditions likely occur at or near the compounds' polar head groups, rather than along the perfluoroalkyl chain. The research conclusively indicates that PFASs like PFOS are significantly more resilient than PFCAs under subcritical water conditions.

PFOS breaks down thermally through recently understood processes. Studies in computational chemistry and reaction rate theory have shown that the main decomposition route for PFOS is the creation of an α -sultone, which rapidly disintegrates into perfluorooctanal and SO₂. Notably, at 1000 K, the half-life of PFOS is as short as 0.2 seconds, and this duration decreases with increasing temperature. This finding suggests that the acid component of PFOS can be efficiently dismantled in incinerators at relatively moderate temperatures, providing crucial insights for enhancing current remediation methods (Li et al, 2022).

Figure 47 illustrates the percentage (%) of target PFAS removed for each experiment conducted at varying pressures during the HTC process of anaerobically digested sludge. All experiments were conducted at 250 °C and anaerobically digested sludge was used as substrate. The results suggest that the different pressures employed during HTC processing do not seem to have an impact on PFAS removal. Five out of seven PFAS were removed at a percentage higher than 94% in all experiments, while PFUdA and PFOS (total and linear) were removed at percentages ranging between 55 and 75%. A slight increase of PFUdA and PFOS removal was observed when the pH increased from 7 to 9 (Figure 45). In a previous study, Wu et al. (2019) explored the influence of NaOH on PFAS decomposition, reporting that NaOH, in conjunction with pH-raising agents, facilitated the breakdown and reduction of fluorine content in PFOS. Similarly, research conducted by Hao et al. (2021) confirmed that rapid degradation and complete removal of PFOS and PFOA can be achieved within hydrothermal water through the addition of NaOH or alternative alkaline substances.

Figure 46. PFAS removal (%) in HTC experiments of anaerobically digested sludge under three different pressure values (applied temperature: 250 °C).

Further experiments at pH 7 and 9 and analysis of PFAS in different outputs of HTC of sludge (hydrochar, HTC liquid, Tar trap condensate, Tar trap gases) showed that the studied PFAS were detected at trace amounts in the gas phase. Application of mass balances showed that the part of target PFAS that passed to the gas phase was lower than 0.001%. No PFAS were detected at the Tar trap condensate.

Figure 48 illustrates the pH values of the samples following each HTC treatment of anaerobically digested sludge at a constant temperature of 250°C but under varying pressures. The observed pH levels are influenced by the increasing pressures applied during the treatment process. An insightful study by Zhi et al. (2023) emphasizes that the pH of the liquid phase is intricately determined by the interplay of acidic and basic functional groups. In scenarios where the reaction intensity is heightened, there is an initial decline in pH levels, followed by a subsequent increase over time (Zhi et al., 2023). This dynamic relationship between pH and the treatment conditions underscores the complexity of the hydrothermal carbonization process and its impact on the sludge's chemical properties. The full range of experiments highlighted that the trend in pH levels displayed an upward trajectory with increasing temperatures. Conversely, the decrease in pH levels observed during HTC at lower temperatures can be elucidated by the hydrolysis reactions taking place at these thermal conditions. These reactions lead to the formation of organic acids from complex organic compounds, subsequently resulting in a decline in the pH of the reaction medium. Notably, this pH shift triggers the dissolution of phosphates that are bound to calcium, as highlighted by Chen et al. (2023). This intricate interplay between temperature, hydrolysis reactions, and the dissolution of phosphate compounds underscores the multifaceted nature of the hydrothermal carbonization process and its intricate chemical transformations.

Figure 47. pH rates of HTC experiments of anaerobically digested sludge under three different pressures (applied temperature: 250 °C).

Figure 49 displays the concentrations of ammonium nitrogen in the liquid samples obtained from HTC experiments conducted using anaerobic digested sludge at varying pressure. A previous study by Garg et al. (2023) reported that during the thermal degradation treatment of sludge, certain proteins undergo incomplete breakdown, resulting in the generation of ammonia. It is noteworthy that as the temperature of the HTC process increased, the $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentration exhibited a corresponding increase. This trend aligns with findings in a study conducted by Fan et al. (2023), where a significant portion of the nitrogen content in the liquid phase originated from $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and demonstrated a substantial rise in concentration with increasing temperature. Furthermore, research conducted by He et al. (2015) emphasized the considerable alteration in the distribution of nitrogen species within the liquid phase, primarily attributed to the elevating temperature and heightened pressure conditions employed in the process. It becomes evident that pressure variations play a substantial role in influencing $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentrations; an initial surge in $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ concentrations was observed as the pressure escalated from 38.3 bar to 40 bar, followed by a subsequent decline when the pressure was further elevated to 65.2 bar. This behaviour aligns with similar trends observed in a study conducted by He et al. (2015), where ammonium nitrogen concentrations exhibited an increase (rising from 4,020 to 6,660 mg/L) when the temperature was raised from 200 °C to 260 °C and the pressure was elevated from 2 to 5 MPa. Subsequently, at higher temperatures (260–320 °C), a decrease in ammonium nitrogen concentrations was noted (ranging between 3,500 and 6,400 mg/L).

Figure 48. Ammonium nitrogen concentrations in HTC experiments of anaerobically digested sludge under three different pressures (applied temperature: 250 °C).

Figure 50 shows the COD concentrations of liquid samples from HTC experiments with anaerobically digested sludge, all conducted at a consistent temperature of 250°C but at varying pressures. Vasileiadou et al. (2022) reported that an increase in pressure corresponded to an increase in COD concentrations. The data here (A – C) is in agreement with these findings.

Figure 50. COD concentrations in HTC experiments of anaerobically digested sludge under three different pressures (applied temperature: 250 °C).

However, it is noteworthy that in the subsequent measurements (D to F), a distinct pattern emerges. Initially, there is a decrease in concentrations in the experiment conducted at 250 bar, followed by another increase at 300 bar. These results are in line

with the outcomes reported in a study by Babu et al. (2023), where it was observed that the addition of NaOH led to an increase in COD concentrations during the hydrothermal treatment. This variation in COD concentrations under different conditions underscores the complexity of the hydrothermal carbonization process and its sensitivity to factors like pressure and pH adjustment. Comparison of the experiments conducted under identical conditions of temperature (250°C) and pressure (38 bar) in the two distinct sludge types, highlights a notable disparity in the COD concentrations observed. Specifically, the COD concentrations of the anaerobically digested sludge subjected to hydrothermal treatment were significantly higher than those of the sewage sludge following the same treatment conditions. This disparity suggests inherent differences in the organic composition or reactivity of the two sludge types under these conditions. Furthermore, it is worth considering that the adjustment of pH to 9 using NaOH may have played a contributing role in the observed increase in COD concentrations. This adjustment likely introduced variations in the chemical environment, potentially impacting the hydrothermal reactions and organic compound breakdown, thus influencing the COD concentrations in the final products.

The phytotoxicity experiments were based on Celletti et al. (2021) and assessed the germination index of the hydrochar extracts from variously treated anaerobic and sewage sludge. The results are presented in Figure 51 and show the increased germination index with increased pressure of treatment, while the presence of PFAS decrease the germination index in all cases of application.

Figure 49. Phytotoxicity test of hydrochar for various temperatures and pressures of hydrothermal carbonization.

The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis is a critical method in the field of material science, particularly important for characterizing the surface area of porous materials. This analysis technique is based on the BET theory, which extends the Langmuir theory to multilayer adsorption, providing a more comprehensive approach to understanding how gases interact with solid surfaces. The specific surface area is a vital parameter in many applications, especially in catalysis, where it can directly influence the catalytic activity of materials. Moreover, BET analysis is essential in fields like pharmaceuticals

but also for potential utilization of given material as an absorbent, due to the valuable information that are provided about pore size distribution and the porosity of materials. The surface area according to the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method and the nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms were determined at 77 Kelvin across various relative pressures using a 3Flex physisorption analyser from Micromeritics. The results are presented in Figure 52, where the surface area and the total pore size of different hydrochars are being presented. There is a clear correlation between the surface are and the total pore size with the pressure of the process and this is an interesting parameter that needs to be considered for applications of hydrochar as an absorbent.

Figure 50. Surface are and total pore size (BET analysis) of hydrochars produced via hydrothermal carbonization in various temperatures and pressures.

5. Conclusions

Significant differences were observed regarding the fate of the two groups of persistent and mobile substances tested in the current study. BTRs were significantly removed during conventional sludge anaerobic digestion and their removal exceeded 95% when GAC was added to the bioreactors. However, PFAS were totally resistant to anaerobic biodegradation in conventional AD bioreactors. The addition of GAC resulted to partial removal (>40%) of most studied PFAS. Differences in their removal were observed depending on the experimental conditions applied and the PFAS itself. Modifications of the AD process via the application of external voltage or/and addition of GAC had positive effects on methane productivity. Additionally, the application of ultrasound sludge pretreatment increased maximum biogas production rate. With the exception of PFOS and PFUdA, the studied PFAS were significantly removed (>85%) during HTC of sludge. Collection and analysis of gas samples from the HTC reactor indicated the existence of trace amounts of PFAS in the gas phase. The increase of temperature from 200 to 300 °C slightly enhanced the removal of PFOS and PFUdA. Characterisation of the liquid produced after sludge HTC showed increase of COD and NH₄⁺-N concentrations, while pH levels were decreased.

The application of the aforementioned technologies and identified optimal parameters from these lab tests will be used in the pilot scale plant. This pilot scale plant is to be constructed at test site 3 and monitoring which will be carried out for two years will allow the evaluation of the system's performance for a greater number of persistent and mobile substances (Deliverable 7.6). Data related to the environmental footprint of the processes and the characteristics of by-products will also be collected (Deliverable 2.5).

6. Acknowledgements

We thank Evdokia Galipidu, Michalis Deligiannis, Rafael Georgiou, Leonidas Koutsellis and Dimitris Kalantzis for their contribution to the elaboration of AD experiments, Georgia Altiparmaki and George Liakos for the elaboration of HTC experiment, Marios Kostakis, Olga Arvaniti, Emma Knight and Andreas Androulakakis for PFAS analysis. We thank the ZeroPM consortium for discussions throughout the project that helped guide the direction of the work.

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8. Appendix

8.1 Determination of conventional pollutants and basic parameters

Total solids (TS), volatile solids (VS), dissolved COD and ammonium nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$) were determined according to APHA (2005). Biogas production in continuous experiments was recorded every 2–3 days using a 2-L gas bag. Specifically, the biogas collected in the bag in a period of 1 h was measured. Methane content was determined using an Agilent 6890 N gas chromatograph supplied with a Thermal Conductivity Detector (TCD) and a capillary column HP-Plot Q (Agilent, USA). The oven temperature was 40 °C for the first 1.5 min and then increased gradually (50 °C/min) to 220 °C. The temperature of the injector and the detector was set at 200 °C and 230 °C, respectively (Kalantzis et al., 2023). VFAs (acetic, propionic, isobutyric, butyric, iso-valeric and valeric acid) were analyzed by Agilent 6890 N gas chromatograph supplied with a Flame Ionization Detector (FID) and a capillary column DB WAXETR (Agilent, USA). The oven temperature was increased from 140 °C to 158 (2 °C/min) and then to 200 °C (20 °C/min). The temperature of the injector was set at 220 °C.

8.2 Determination of benzotriazoles

8.2.1 Sample preparation

50 mL of filtered wastewater was transferred into a 50 mL Eppendorf tube and adjusted to pH 3.00 (± 0.10). Extraction was performed by StrataTM-X cartridges. The cartridges were conditioned by passage of 2x5 mL of MeOH and equilibrated by 2x5 mL of acidified Milli-Q water (adjusted with HCl solution to pH 3.00 ± 0.10). Then, the acidified samples were passed through the cartridges. In order to remove any matrix interferences, the cartridges were washed with 2x5 mL of acidified Milli-Q water (adjusted with HCl to pH 3.00 ± 0.10) and then dried under vacuum. The compounds were eluted with 2x5 mL of mixture of MeOH/ACN (1:1 v/v). The eluents were set on a heated tray (45 °C) and were evaporated to near-dryness, under a gentle stream of nitrogen gas (N_2). Then, the eluents were diluted to 1 mL with 75% H_2O -25% ACN filtered and transferred into a vial for analysis (Asimakopoulos et al., 2013).

8.2.2. Instrumental analysis

Chromatographic analysis of the samples was performed based on a previously developed method by Mazioti et al. (2015) using a Shimadzu (Japan) LC20-AD prominence liquid chromatographer associated with a SPD-M20A diode array detector (DAD) and a SIL-20AC auto sampler. The column was a Zorbax SB-C18 4.6 mm \times 150 mm (5 μm) connected with a Zorbax SB-C18 pre-column (Agilent, USA). The column and pre-column were heated at 35 °C with a CTO-20AC column oven (Shimadzu-Japan). The mobile phase consisted of MilliQ grade water 0.05% acetic acid (solvent A) and ACN (solvent B). Gradient elution was performed as

follows: from 25% ACN to 75% ACN in 15 min, hold for 9 min and then decrease to 25% ACN in 1 min. The system was equilibrated for 10 min with 25% ACN before each run. The total duration of the separation program was 35 min and the flow rate was 0.5 mL min⁻¹. All compounds were quantified using the signal at 254 nm. The identification of the five compounds in the sample was accomplished on the basis of their retention times and comparing their UV spectrum in the standard solutions and in the samples.

8.3 Determination of PFAS

8.3.1 Continuous anaerobic digestion and hydrothermal carbonization experiments

8.3.1.1 Sample preparation

An aliquot of 50 mL of filtered wastewater (applies to all liquid samples) was transferred into a 50 mL Eppendorf tube and adjusted to pH = 4.0 ± 0.1 with acetic acid solution 1 M prior to the loading step of the solid phase extraction (SPE). All samples prior to SPE were vortex mixed for 1 min. Extraction and isolation of target analytes from the samples were performed using Oasis HLB cartridges. The cartridges were conditioned by passage of 2x3 mL of MeOH and equilibrated by 2x5 mL of Milli-Q grade water. Then, the samples were passed through the cartridges. In order to remove any matrix interference, the cartridges were washed with 2 mL of MeOH/Milli-Q water (40:60, % v/v) and then dried under vacuum. The compounds were eluted with 4x1 mL MeOH and collected in a 15 mL Eppendorf tube. The eluents were evaporated to dryness under a gentle stream of nitrogen gas (N₂). Then, the eluents were diluted to 500 µL with MeOH, filtered and transferred for analysis (Arvaniti et al., 2012).

An aliquot of 100 mg (±10 mg) dewatered sludge was transferred into a 50 mL Eppendorf tube and mixture of 7.5 mL of 1% v/v acetic acid and 1.5 mL of MeOH was added. Then liquid–solid extraction (LSE) was performed by vortex-mixing for 1 min followed by ultra-sonicated for 15 min. The supernatant was collected after centrifugation (×1) at 3500 rpm for 15 min. The LSE procedure was performed totally three successive times for each sample (3 × 7.5 mL), and all three supernatants were transferred into a 50 mL Eppendorf tube. Dilution was performed to 50 mL with Milli-Q grade water. Then, SPE extraction was performed using the procedure as aforementioned for the dissolved phase of the samples.

8.3.1.2 Instrumental analysis

An Exion HPLC system coupled to a Sciex QTRAP mass spectrometer 6500⁺ (Sciex, Canada) was used for the qualitative and quantitative determination of PFAS compounds in the samples.

LC parameters:

Delay column: XBridge™ C18 2.5 µm 2.1x50 mm

Pre-column: SecurityGuard™ Guard Cartridge Kit, Phenomenex

Column: Xterra® MS C18 3.5 µm 2.1x100 mm

Column oven: 40 °C

Injection volume 10.0 µL

Mobile Phase:

A: MeOH

B: Buffer 5 mM ammonium acetate, 5 mM 1-methyl-piperidine

Flow: 0.3 mL/min

Gradient elution:		
Time	%A	%B
0	10	90
3.00	10	90
3.10	40	60
26.00	90	10
28.00	90	10
29.00	10	90
32.00	10	90

MS parameters:

Qtrap system: negative ESI mode

IonSpray Voltage (IS): -4500.0

Temperature (TEM): 250.0

Collision Gas (CAD): Medium

Curtain gas (CUR): 40.0

Ion Source Gas 1 (GS1): 35.0

Ion Source Gas 2 (GS2): 35.0

Table 9. MS parameters for the target compounds measured in this study.

Compound		Q1 Mass (Da)	Q3 Mass (Da)	Dwell Time (msec)	DP (Volts)	EP (Volts)	CE (Volts)	CXP (Volts)	Rt (min)
PFPeA	Quantifier	263	219	20	-20	-8	-11	-20	6.43
	Qualifier	263	69	20	-5	-10	-58	-9	
PFHpA	Quantifier	363	319	20	-17	-10	-14	-26	10.63
	Qualifier	363	169	20	-32	-11	-25	-24	
PFOA	Quantifier	413	369	20	-130	-10	-14	-21	13.08
	Qualifier	413	169	20	-130	-10	-24	-7	
PFNA	Quantifier	463	419	20	-145	-10	-16	-27	15.28
	Qualifier	463	219	20	-145	-10	-24	-15	
PFDA	Quantifier	513	469	20	-15	-10	-16	-29	17.38
	Qualifier	513	269	20	-20	-10	-26	-17	
PFUdA	Quantifier	563	519	20	-25	-10	-18	-13	18.76
	Qualifier	563	269	20	-25	-10	-26	-15	
PFOS	Quantifier	498	80	20	-125	-10	-92	-9	15.64
	Qualifier	498	99	20	-125	-10	-92	-9	
M4PFOS	IS	502.94	79.96	20	-60	-10	-100	-9	15.42

8.3.2 Hydrothermal carbonization mass balance experiment and batch anaerobic digestion experiments

8.3.2.1 Sample preparation

1 g of dried sludge was spiked with isotopically labelled internal standard ^{13}C -PFAS mix (30 μL of 0.1 ppm) and left for 30 min. Then, a mixture of 5 mL of MeOH/NH₃ (aq) (99/1) was added and extraction was performed by agitation for 30 min followed by sonication for 30 min. The supernatant was collected after centrifugation ($\times 1$) at 2700 rpm for 10 min. The extraction procedure was repeated using 3 mL of MeOH/NH₃ (aq) (99/1) this time. The two supernatants were combined and reduced in volume to 1 mL under a gentle stream of nitrogen gas (N₂). The concentrated samples were acidified with acetic acid and cleaned up using a Bond Elut Carbon cartridge (100mg, Agilent Technologies), previously pre-conditioned with 1 mL of methanol. The cartridges were rinsed with 1 mL of methanol and the diluted samples were again concentrated to 1 mL by nitrogen gas (N₂). Finally, an aliquot of 0.2 mL of each sample was subjected to LS-MS/MS analysis after the addition of 0.1 mL of ammonium acetate solution (5.2 mM) (Bräunig et al., 2017; Higgins and Luthy, 2006).

8.3.2.2 Instrumental analysis

For the analysis of the samples a UPLC-MS/MS system was used.

LC parameters:

Instrument: Acquity UPLC, Waters

Run time: 9 min

Mobile phase A: 5.2 mM ammonium acetate in ultra-pure water

Mobile phase B: Acetonitrile:methanol, 3:1 (v/v)

Flow rate: 0.5 mL/min

Column: ACQUITY UPLC BEH C8 1.7 μ m

Column temperature: 50 °C

Injection volume: 2 μ L

Table 10. Mobile phase gradient over nine-minute run time.

Time (min)	A%	B%
0.0	92	8.0
1.0	92	8.0
7.0	0.0	100
8.0	0.0	100
8.1	92	8.0
9.0	92	8.0

MS parameters:

Instrument: Xevo TQ-S, Waters

Electro-spray ionisation: negative mode

Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM)

Table 11. Mass-labelled standards used for each of the target PFAS.

Native	Internal std	Surrogate	Additional Internal std
PFPeA		M5PFHxA, M3PFHxS	MPFOS
PFOA	M8PFOA		MPFOS
PFNA	M9PFNA		MPFOS
PFOS	M8PFOS		MPFOS
PFDA	M6PFDA		MPFOS
PFUnDA	M7PFUnDA		MPFOS

Table 12. LC- MS/MS parameters for each target analyte.

PFAS	Retention time (min)	Parent m/z	Daughter (m/z)	Cone (V)	Collison (V)
PFPeA	3.48	263	219	10	9
PFOA	4.72	412	369	15	11
PFNA	5.02	463	419	15	11
PFOS	5.24	498	88 99	30 30	30 27
PFDA	5.28	513	469	15	13
PFUnDA	5.53	563	519	15	13

8.4 High-throughput 16 S rRNA gene sequencing

For the evaluation of the microbial profile of the sludge, samples were taken at the end of the experimental phase from the different bioreactors operating at thermophilic phase (Experiment D). Each sample, approximately 250 mg, underwent DNA extraction using the DNeasy Power Soil Pro Kit (Qiagen, Germany). The extracted genomic DNA was then sent to DNASense ApS (Denmark) for analysis, following the methodology outlined by Gatidou et al. (2022). More specifically, for the PCR amplification, universal primers targeting the 16S rRNA gene were used. Specifically, the 515FB primer (GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA) served as the forward primer, and the 1391R primer (GACGGGCGGTGGWTRCA) was used as the reverse primer. These primers are well-suited for amplifying a wide range of microbial DNA, thereby providing a comprehensive overview of the microbial communities in the samples. The PCR conditions were meticulously set: an initial denaturation at 98°C for 3 minutes, followed by 25 cycles of amplification (each cycle comprising 98°C for 30 seconds, 62°C for 20 seconds, and 72°C for 2 minutes), and a final elongation step at 72°C for 5 minutes.

8.5 Phytotoxicity assessment

Phytotoxicity tests were conducted following the method described by Celletti et al. (2021). Initially, hydrochar extracts were prepared by diluting them with Milli-Q water (1/100 w/v). Then, the samples were vigorously shaken for 2 h at maximum speed and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 5 min at room temperature. Finally, they were filtered (VWR filter papers, pore size of 10–20 µm). For the germination tests, two layers of absorbent paper (Whatman No. 42 filter paper), 1.2 mL of the diluted hydrochar extract and seeds of Cress plant (*Lepidum Sativum*) were placed in each petri dish. The petri dishes were sealed with parafilm, covered with aluminium foil and incubated for 48 hrs at 24°C. After the 48-hour incubation, the germinated seeds were counted, and their total root lengths were measured in both the treated and control samples. All germination tests were performed in triplicates. The dilution used for the phytotoxicity experiments was selected after conducting four trials with different dilutions (1/10, 1/40, 1/80, 1/100) in hydrochar extracts obtained from for various temperatures and pressures of hydrothermal carbonization of anaerobic sludge (AS) and sewage sludge (SS).